

Decomposition of quantitative Gaifman graphs as a data analysis tool

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Abstract. We argue the usefulness of Gaifman graphs of first-order relational structures as an exploratory data analysis tool. We illustrate our approach with cases where the modular decompositions of these graphs reveal interesting facts about the data. Then, we introduce generalized notions of Gaifman graphs, enhanced with quantitative information, to which we can apply more general, existing decomposition notions via 2-structures; thus enlarging the analytical capabilities of the scheme. The very essence of Gaifman graphs makes this approach immediately appropriate for the multirelational data framework.

1 Introduction

First-order (finite) relational structures (see e.g. [10]) are the conceptual essence of the relational database model. In fact, relational databases, often composed of multiple relations (or: “tables”) have been a key figure in the theory and practice of Computation for decades.

Gaifman graphs are a well-known, quite natural theoretical construction that can be applied to any relational structure [10]. They have provided very interesting progress in the theory of these logical models. As we shall see here, it pays off to study datasets through decompositions of their associated Gaifman graphs.

We extend the data analysis capabilities of the scheme by generalizing, in very natural ways, the notion of Gaifman graph so as to handle quantitative information. Indeed, in its basic form, Gaifman graphs are, as are their corresponding first-order relational structures, plainly Boolean: we will propose several natural ideas to enhance their symbolic capabilities through different ways of considering quantitative information. Then, we propose to consider a correspondingly generalized form of modular decomposition, namely, the decomposition of 2-structures [5], again a notion that has been very fruitfully developed in their theoretical form, and in a number of applications (such as [9]), but not yet imported, to our knowledge, into the data analysis framework.

Conceptually, the data analysis scheme obtained can be applied directly in a context of multirelational data analysis [13]. A preliminary, “proof-of-concept”, freely available system has been implemented to perform this sort of exploratory data analysis by computing and decomposing generalized Gaifman graphs out of given multirelational data. Admittedly, its functionality, efficiency and (mainly) usability leave ample room for improvement. But, as we shall see here, it already allows us to argue the potential value of this approach for data analysis.

2 Decomposing standard Gaifman graphs

The basic notion of Gaifman graph is pretty simple. Given a first-order relational structure, or relational database, with relations R_i , where the values in the tuples come from a fixed universe U , the corresponding Gaifman graph has the elements of U as vertices; and there is an edge (x, y) , for $x \neq y$, exactly when x and y appear together in some tuple $t \in R_i$ for some table R_i .

Example 1. As a running example, let us consider a very small, single-relation database on the universe $\{a, b, c, d, e\}$, with three attributes and three tuples:

$t_1: a b c$

$t_2: a d e$

$t_3: a c d$

Then, the Gaifman graph is as shown in Figure 1 (left).

Fig. 1. A Gaifman graph, its natural completion, and a labeled variant.

In this example we see values c and d as valid values for both the second and the third attributes. Often, in practice, each column of a table has its own semantics and, even if a data value seems to superficially coincide in occurrences at different columns, it might mean different things (e.g. the same string “yes” as a value of columns named “homeowner” and “haschildren” might prompt us to consider them as different values). We assume that a preprocessing has been run so that, if domain information was available advising data pieces to be considered different, then these are already represented by different values of the universe U (e.g. the strings “haschildren:yes” and “homeowner:yes”).

2.1 Some cosmetics on Gaifman graphs

In order to facilitate our later developments, we chose to see the Gaifman graph in an equivalent form: as a complete graph with two sorts of (nonreflexive) edges.

One sort corresponds to edges present in the original Gaifman graph formulation (we represent them as solid lines in our diagrams); the other corresponds to (nonreflexive) edges absent in the original formulation (we represent them as broken lines). We call this graph the “natural completion” of the original graph. In our example, this process is illustrated in Figure 1 (center).

Additionally, sometimes we will label each edge with its multiplicity, that is, the number of tuples that contain the pair of items linked by the edge. The previous example then becomes as in Figure 1 (right): pairs appear either zero times together (dashed edges), once (black lines, labeled 1) or, in two cases, twice (gray lines, labeled 2).

2.2 2-structures and their decompositions

A very classical notion called “modular decomposition” [7] suffices to implement our approach on plain Gaifman graphs; this notion has been rediscovered many times and described under several different names¹. However, it is insufficient to handle adequately the generalizations that we propose below: we develop our system directly on top of the more general notion of 2-structures and their clans [5].

A 2-structure is simply the complete graph on some universe U , plus an equivalence relation E among the edges. Figure 1 (right) serves as an example, where there are three equivalence classes of edges: the broken edges, the black edges, and the gray edges; of course, Figure 1 (center) is also an example, with just two equivalence classes of edges. We will restrict ourselves to undirected edges, and will employ the common, very graphical and intuitive representation of coloring in the same way edges belonging to the same equivalence class.

Observe that the type of the equivalence relation E is $E \subseteq ((U \times U) \times (U \times U))$ because E tells us whether two arbitrary edges (x, y) and (u, v) are equivalent.

This combinatorial concept can be studied in a number of ways; for example, somewhat unrelated to our study, a notion of “region” gives rise to a connection with Petri nets [1]. In our development, we focus on the notion of a “clan”.

For a 2-structure given by the set of vertices U and the equivalence relation E among the edges of the complete graph on U , we say that a subset $C \subseteq U$ is a clan, informally, if all the members of C are indistinguishable among them by non-members. That is: whenever some $x \notin C$ “can distinguish” between $y \in C$ and $z \in C$, in the sense that the edge (x, y) is not equivalent to the edge (x, z) , then C is *not* a clan. Formally (see [5]):

Definition 1. *Given U and an equivalence relation $E \subseteq ((U \times U) \times (U \times U))$ on the edges of the complete graph on U , $C \subseteq U$ is a clan when*

$$\forall x \notin C \forall y \in C \forall z \in C ((x, y), (x, z)) \in E.$$

Note that different vertices outside the clan might see the clan differently: for $x \notin C$ and $x' \notin C$, and $y \in C$, the edges (x, y) and (x', y) may well be

¹ See https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Modular_decomposition for some of the alternative names that the concept has received.

nonequivalent (this is where the alternative approach of “regions” mentioned before departs from our approach). We only require that each fixed x does not distinguish between the clan members.

Basic examples of clans are the so-called trivial clans: all the singletons $\{x\}$ for $x \in U$, as well as U itself, are vacuously clans. There may be other clans. For instance, consider the natural completion of the Gaifman graph obtained from Example 1, depicted in Figure 1 (center). Edges are split into two equivalence classes (existing or nonexisting edges in the original Gaifman graph). Then, one can see that there would be exactly one nontrivial clan, formed by $\{b, c, d, e\}$: all vertices not in the clan (that is, vertex a , the single one not in the clan) are connected to each vertex inside the clan through edges of the same color, namely solid black. Any other candidate turns out not to be a clan. For instance, any set including a and b but excluding e is not a clan, as e “distinguishes” between a and b ; then, any set including b and e must include c and d , which can distinguish between them. All in all, any clan including a and b ends up including all the vertices, that is, becoming a trivial clan. Analogous reasoning applies if we start by pairing a with other vertices.

On the other hand, it is not difficult to see that the labeled, colored version of the Gaifman graph of Example 1, as depicted in Figure 1 (right), does not have nontrivial clans. Equivalence is given by the same multiplicity label (that is, edges drawn in the same “color”): the extra distinction between gray and black edges allows for external vertices to distinguish between some vertices inside every candidate proper subset. Further examples come later as clans are the key tool for our proposal of a data analysis method.

2.3 Prime clans and tree decompositions

It is known [5] that certain clans, called prime clans, allow us to decompose a 2-structure into a tree-like form.

Definition 2. *For a fixed universe U , we say that two subsets of U overlap if neither is a subset of the other, but they are not disjoint. That is, for $S \subseteq U$ and $T \subseteq U$, they overlap if the three sets $S \cap T$, $S \setminus T$, and $T \setminus S$ are all three nonempty. Then, prime clans are those clans that do not overlap any other clan.*

Of course, trivial clans are also immediately prime clans. Thus, by definition, any two sets in the family of prime clans are either disjoint, or a subset of one another: they provide us with a so-called “decomposable set family” [12] that can be pictured in a tree form, by displaying every prime clan (except U itself) as a child of the smallest prime clan that properly contains it.

There are studies that report how these decompositions look like. Specifically, at each node of the tree we have again a 2-structure, whose vertices correspond to the clans that fall as children of the node. In the case of our constructions out of Gaifman graphs, it is known that all the 2-structures that appear as nodes of such a tree decomposition are of one of two well-defined sorts: either “complete” (all edges are equivalent) or “primitive” (only having trivial clans).

This is due to our graphs being undirected, because 2-structures on directed graphs may exhibit a third basic component in their tree decomposition (“linear” 2-structures). Further information on this topic appears in [5]. This reference contains, as well, often far-from-trivial proofs of theorems that ensure that things are as we have described.

Example 2. Continuing Example 1, the tree decomposition of the 2-structure in Figure 1 (center) is displayed in Figure 2 (left). Boxes correspond to clans: here, the topmost box corresponds to the trivial clan containing all the vertices and, inside it, each dot corresponds to a prime subclan. All along the whole decomposition, trivial clans are indicated by a link to the vertex they consist of, represented with an elliptic node; nontrivial ones are linked instead to a new box describing the internal structure of the clan, in terms of the prime clans it has as proper subsets. Then, as a set, each clan is formed by all the elements in the leaves of the subtree rooted at it.

2.4 Limits to the visualization of complex clans

Our experimentation shows that, unsurprisingly, the visualization of large Gaifman graphs is unadvisable. Actually, sometimes the clans lead to large primitive 2-structures, whose mathematical study gets pretty complicated [6]. We set up some relatively arbitrary limits, trying to get understandable diagrams. Let us consider a more realistic example to explain them.

In Figure 2 (right) we display (a fragment of) the decomposition of the Gaifman graph of the well-known Zoo dataset from the UC Irvine repository [3]; it contains 17 attributes of 100 animal species. We have preprocessed it slightly so that the semantics of each item is clearly identifiable (e. g. `predator_False` or `toothed_True`). We will return to this dataset below in Section 4.2.

For the time being, we just discuss the decomposition of its standard Gaifman graph. The topmost node of this decomposition is, as always, the trivial clan with the whole universe; in this case, it turns out to decompose as a set of many trivial clans, set up in the form of a primitive 2-structure that we choose not to draw complete; however, one nontrivial clan also appears: “mammal” and “milk_True” are indistinguishable from the perspective of all the other elements in the dataset. That is, for every other piece of information, either it goes together with each in some tuples (one such item could be “hair_True”), or it does not go together with any of them ever (for instance: “feathers_True”).

In our diagrams, as we do here, clans containing more than a handful of nontrivial clans are not drawn in detail: just the clan type label (“primitive” or “complete”) is shown. Besides, if there are few nontrivial clans, but many trivial ones, then the trivial clans are grouped in a single node labeled Others, sort of a merge of them all. The reader must keep in mind that this particular node actually represents together a number of unstructured items.

This approach of limiting the size of the substructures that become fully spelled-out was taken also in [9], where also a “zooming” capability was introduced (we may consider adding one such option to our system in the future).

Fig. 2. Decompositions of the Gaifman graphs for Example 1 and for the Zoo dataset.

2.5 Isolated vertex elision

As we move on, later, into quantitative generalizations of Gaifman graphs, one case turns out to be common in our experiments. Whereas Gaifman graphs do not have isolated vertices (except in limit, artificial cases such as relations with a single attribute), in our generalizations this is no longer true: many datasets will lead to 2-structures exhibiting many vertices that are endpoints only of broken edges; that is, they are isolated vertices in the corresponding (generalized) Gaifman graph. The set of those isolated vertices forms a sometimes quite large clan that clutters the diagram but contributes nothing to the analysis beyond “all these vertices are actually isolated”. We use again the label “Others” to represent these items, all alike from the decomposition perspective, as a single vertex, as indeed this is a particular case of the usage of the “Others” label as per the previous Section 2.4.

2.6 Algorithmics and implementation

A couple of published algorithms [11, 12] can be adapted for implementing a system computing this sort of tree decompositions. However, as we envision an analysis support system able to add Gaifman nodes in an incremental manner, we have implemented a somewhat different, incremental algorithm. Due to the space limit, the details of our algorithmic contributions will be presented in a future version of this paper, together with some comparisons against other algorithms. A first “brute-force”, exhaustive search attempt was employed in [14] to identify all prime clans; although it ended up being far too slow for any practical purposes, it was sufficient to provide us with a small number of case studies that showed that this exploratory data analysis process was interesting.

We have resorted to a relatively simple implementation in Python, <https://github.com/MelyPic/PrimeTreeDecomposition>, relying on the standard graph module NetworkX and on the graphical capabilities of the `pydot` interface to the Dot engine of Graphviz [8].

3 Interpreting a decomposition of a Gaifman graph

We move on to explain another example of our analysis strategy. We present and discuss the outcome of a tree decomposition of the Gaifman graph of a simple, famous, and relatively small dataset often used for teaching introductory data analysis courses. It comes from data of each of the passengers of the Titanic. Among several existing variants of this dataset, some of them pretty complete, we choose a reduced variant on which we illustrate the interpretation of our decompositions. This variant we use keeps four attributes, one of them (age) discretized. To describe the details of this dataset, we quote:

“The titanic dataset gives the values of four categorical attributes for each of the 2201 people on board the Titanic when it struck an iceberg and sank. The attributes are social class (first class, second class, third class, crewmember), age (adult or child), sex, and whether or not the person survived.”

(<http://www.cs.toronto.edu/~delve/data/titanic/desc.html>)

(As indicated in that website, this variant of the data was originally compiled by Dawson [2] and converted for use in the DELVE data analysis environment by Radford Neal.)

The decomposition via its standard Gaifman graph is depicted in Figure 3. Recall that broken edges represent pairs that never appear together in any tuple, whereas solid edges are edges of the original Gaifman graph and thus join universe elements that appear together in some tuple.

The clans for sex and survival are clear and intuitive: as they are different possible values for the same attribute, they never appear together.

Likewise, one might expect a clan with the four alternative values of traveling class, namely, 1st, 2nd, 3rd or Crew. However, the value Crew migrates to the parent clan and interacts with the age clan, forming a small primitive 2-structure there: this calls our attention to the fact that the crew included, of course, no children, a fact that we might overlook in a non-systematic analysis. That is: even if the traveling class and the “Crew” label are employed as values in the same column, the data tells us, through our decomposition procedure, that they have different semantics!

4 Generalizations of Gaifman graphs

We move on to discuss tree decompositions based on generalized Gaifman graphs. The aim is to keep track of quantitative information that the standard Gaifman graph lacks: data analysis often requires one to handle quantitative information. Then, the power of our approach is further revealed by the enhancements obtained through these generalized notions, novel to our knowledge.

In our context, many ideas present themselves to complement Gaifman graphs and clan decompositions with quantitative considerations. For the time being, we contemplate just some very simple cases: we let the number of occurrences of each pair play a role. Recall that we keep this value as a label of the corresponding edge, recording its multiplicity.

Fig. 3. Decomposing the standard Gaiifman graph of the Titanic dataset.

In fact, all these generalizations of Gaiifman graphs, being complete and with “colored edges” that define an equivalence relation, are actually 2-structures, each equivalence class on edges being defined through the occurrence multiplicities and the corresponding “color”; and they can be decomposed as such, in terms of their prime clans, as we will do. However, we find handy to keep referring to them as graphs.

4.1 Thresholded Gaiifman graphs

Our first variant is as follows.

Definition 3. For a threshold k (a nonzero natural number) a thresholded Gaiifman graph is a completion of a Gaiifman graph in which each labeled edge is classified according to its number of occurrences, as follows. We still have two equivalence classes of edges. If the number in the label is above the threshold k , the edge goes into one equivalence class (represented in our diagrams by a solid line); whereas if the number of occurrences of the edge is less than or equal to the threshold, then the edge belongs to the other equivalence class (and a broken line is used to represent it).

Figure 4 provides an alternative analysis of the Titanic dataset described before. There, we decompose a thresholded Gaiifman graph, aiming at uncovering very common co-occurrences, that is, high multiplicities. We set the threshold rather arbitrarily at the quite high value of 1000 (out of 2201 tuples). We see at work the effect of isolated vertex elision, as many attribute values to not reach multiplicity 1000 with any other value: the elision process, as described in Section 2.5, replaces all of them by a single node, playing the same role all of them play, that is, broken lines among themselves and to all the surviving values. The new decomposition is interesting in that it very clearly reflects the Birkenhead Drill: “Women and children first”.

Fig. 4. Titanic dataset: thresholded Gaifman graph, at 1000, and its decomposition.

4.2 Quantitative Gaifman graphs

Further additional generalizations seem to be useful; we describe some here.

The *linear colored Gaifman graph* is a (completion of a) Gaifman graph in which the equivalence classes of the edges are directly defined by the label, that is, the number of occurrences. All pairs occurring once would lead to one class, those occurring twice to another, and so on; up to some limit, beyond which we do not keep the distinction. Figure 1 (right) corresponds to this case.

A natural variation is to have each color stand for some interval of values, with linearly growing limits; the case just described would correspond to intervals of width 1. As an example, Figure 5 shows the result of applying intervals of width 25 over the Zoo dataset. Since the maximum multiplicity of the edges in the Gaifman graph of Zoo is 81, we obtain four equivalence classes, but we do not see all of them: this is due simply to our visualization limits. Broken lines mark less than 25 occurrences, solid lines less than 50, and the gray line appearing inside one of the clans goes beyond that limit because it gathers all birds and all fish and all insects into the oviparous clan.

This notion can be combined naturally with the previous one: instead of broken lines being simply the first interval, we can apply a different value as threshold and leave as broken lines all occurrence multiplicities below it, and then use the colors for the values at the threshold or above it, at linearly growing intervals of fixed width. Likewise, an upper threshold can be imposed. For instance, on the Titanic data, we used colors by width 1 intervals up to an upper threshold of 10: this approach is able to point out for us, with no particular user guidance, the fact that the number of children among the first-class travelers was surprisingly small: as it happened to Crew, the first-class node migrates from the traveling-class clan to the age clan.

We have also found useful the *exponential colored Gaifman graph*: while similar in spirit to the intervals in linear graphs, here the interval width grows exponentially: each equivalence class (or color) represents an exponentially growing interval of occurrence multiplicities. Again, as with the linear case, we can also impose a user-defined threshold below which, or over which, the occurrences are not considered different; then, one runs the exponential count between them.

Fig. 5. Decomposing the linear Gaifman graph of Zoo with 25 as interval width.

5 Additional considerations

Of course, we can run this sort of processes directly on graphs. Seen as relational structures, graphs are their own Gaifman graph, so we can simply apply the tree decomposition on the given graph.

However, a couple of extra possibilities naturally arise. For instance, we could decompose a 2-structure where the equivalence classes come from the lengths of the shortest paths between vertices, or from thresholding these lengths; or from the vertex- or edge-connectivity (equivalently, min-cuts, by Menger’s theorem), again possibly thresholded.

5.1 The multirelational perspective

Our examples so far fall into the very common and standard “single table” perspective. However, from their earliest inception, Gaifman graphs were a multirelational concept by essence. Applying tree decompositions of generalized Gaifman graphs to multirelational datasets is, therefore, conceptually immediate.

As an example, we applied our approach to the UW-CSE dataset from the Relational Dataset Repository². For lack of space we omit the figure; let us just mention that the decomposition of the exponential colored Gaifman graph at threshold 30, that we tried somewhat arbitrarily, gave us clear hints at the different properties of the two communities of professors and students, where the first ones have positions whereas the students become easily ranked along the successive academic phases.

² <http://relational.fit.cvut.cz>.

6 Discussion and subsequent work

We have described a data analysis approach based on the prime tree decomposition of variations of the Gaifman graph of a dataset. We have illustrated the process with some relatively successful cases. However, some further observations are in order, so as to provide additional perspective.

First and foremost, we must discuss a clear limitation. Like in so many other exploratory data analysis frameworks, for a given dataset we may not be lucky: it may happen that a given selection of Gaifman graph, once decomposed, has no nontrivial clans, or decomposes into just a few quite large primitive substructures that provide little or no insight about the data. For one, the linear Gaifman graph of the well-known toy dataset Weather (discussed e.g. in [15]) has only trivial clans and, if fully displayed, leads to just a large box of colored spaghetti. Useful advice to choose properly sorts of Gaifman graphs, thresholds, and interval widths remains to be found. After all, parameter tuning is a black art in many data mining approaches.

One natural variant consists of combining the constraints defining clans with those of standard frequent-set mining; we explored that avenue and, unfortunately, in all our attempts, we never found a single case of nontrivial clans.

Regarding further work, there is a long route ahead. First, a companion paper will discuss and compare the available algorithms, a task for which there is no room left in this submission. Also, the variants on graphs hinted at in Section 5 must be developed and their usefulness tested.

The multiplicity-based generalizations we have proposed are quite basic; more sophisticated approaches to define the equivalence relation between edges might be advantageous. In particular, we believe now that some advances might come from the study of the applicability of unsupervised discretization methods [4]. Indeed, the actual multiplicities appearing as labels of the edges of the Gaifman graph (or, alternatively, labels regarding connectivity as discussed in the beginning of Section 5) form a set of integers that is to be discretized in a number of intervals in an unsupervised manner. A few existing algorithms for unsupervised discretization can be applied to try and automatize parts of the transformation of the labeled Gaifman graph into the starting 2-structure.

Besides the theoretical developments, improving the software tool is also a desirable endeavor. Initially, we found the very notion of exploratory data analysis via 2-structure decompositions of quantitative versions of Gaifman graphs risky enough, and were not eager to compute very fast, nor in a very usable way by other people, results that, in principle, were candidates to be fully useless. However, we found our initial results (mostly as we have described here) clearly sufficient to consider that this approach is worth of further effort: we did design better algorithms than the ones initially employed [14], and we are confident that our tool will see considerable improvements along several facets in the coming months: the exploration of alternative tree visualizations, the implementation of additional control like zooming, or the possibility of importing the data directly from databases; this last extension is actually crucial in order to try our methods on the usual multirelational benchmarks.

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